

International Teacher Education

Optimising Classroom Design for Social-Emotional Learning

*A Critical Inquiry of Change Regarding the Classroom Design as the Third Teacher and the
Connecting Social-Emotional Learning Outcomes of Students*

Student name	Hannah Massaro
Student number	██████████
NHL- e-mail address	██████████@██████████.██████████
Specialisation (ITESS only)	
Progress course code	ITEB25V4CCP-A
Supervisor(s)	Marcel Haagsma
Examiner(s)	Marcel Haagsma
Assessment date	18.05.2026

By handing in this product, I declare that the product is my own work and that it is free of plagiarism.

Signature:

Hannah Massaro H.

Abstract

This is a Critical Inquiry of Change (CIC) that seeks to explore the ways in which target redesign can be implemented, using this case study of a mixed Year 1/2 class based in a private international British school in Madrid, Spain such that it will enhance students' social-emotional learning (SEL). Melded into a context where the formative years of the school building, though erected as an office, are far from nurturing an inclusive learning environment – rife with long-standing issues associated with overbearing zoning, poor intakes of natural light and a proliferation in unhealthy spatial units typically associated with care environments but poorly adapted in this case. The study was then conducted using Design-Based Research (DBR), which involved nine weeks of exploring empathy, defining the problem, ideation, prototyping and testing. Data collection consisted of six semi-structured interviews with members of the school leadership (Head of School, Head of Primary, school psychologist and PSHE teacher pre-intervention and post-intervention), a Microsoft Forms questionnaire filled in by eight participants from the teaching and support staff plus a pre-intervention & post-intervention questionnaires with twelve Year 1 & Year 2 students and children sketching their dream classroom that presented as collaborative work. Big ideas to make changes in the classroom were as new set of Seating Arrangements (Chairs), Flexible Zoning (Calm Corner Tent), Positive Word Affirmations on Mirrors, Trolley with Materials, Adjusted Lighting Window Blinds, and material with diverse cultural backgrounds being shown. Both qualitative and quantitative analysis indicate considerable indices of improvement in the students' sense of belonging, emotional regulation and cooperative behaviours as evidenced by observations reported by staff pre-intervention and following a successful intervention. It renders

a theoretically viable, practically replicable and both physically and economically inexpensive prototype for international teaching environments.

Keywords: social-emotional learning, classroom design, design-based research, third teacher, international primary education, belonging, self-regulation.

Table of Contents

Abstract.....	2
Introduction.....	7
Scope and Impact of SEL in Connection to Classroom Design	7
Historical and Contemporary Use of Non-Purpose-Built Buildings	9
Identified Problem and School Context.....	11
Literature Review and Theoretical Framework	14
The Classroom as Third Teacher	14
Theoretical Framework.....	15
Design Based Research and the Design Cycle	17
Key Words	19
Methodology	21
Research Design.....	21
Participants and Context	22
Data Collection Methods	23
Semi-structured interviews with school leadership and specialist staff.....	23
Teacher questionnaire Targets: Microsoft Forms	24
Student baseline questionnaire based on Microsoft Forms.....	24
Drawings made by children: classroom now and dream classroom.....	25
Work on Garland (class bunting activity) in a group.....	25
Before-and-after classroom photographs.....	26
Data Analysis Procedures	26
Ethical Considerations	27
Researcher Positionality.....	27
Universal Design Learning Principles	28
Findings	29
Design-Based Research Cycle Overview	29
Phase 1: Empathise and Define.....	29
Phase 2: Ideate and Co-Design	35
Phase 3: Prototype.....	36
Design and Rationale for 3D Modelling as an Intervention Tool.....	44
Impact of Spatial Redesign on Student Behaviour and Learning.....	45
Phase 4: Reflect and Test.....	45
3D Modelling as a Tool for Scalable Pedagogical Change and Teacher Professional Development.....	47

Discussion.....	48
Classroom Environment as a Tool for SEL Development.....	48
Triangulation and Validity of Findings.....	48
Spatial Predictability and Self-Regulation.....	48
Emotional Impact of the Redesigned Environment.....	49
Practical Implications for Low-Cost Classroom Design	49
Conclusions.....	52
Limitations	54
References.....	55
Appendices.....	59
Appendix 1A: Consent form shared with adults (teachers and specialists).....	59
.....	60
.....	61
Appendix 1B: Consent form shared with parents of the students.....	62
.....	62
Appendix 2A: Microsoft questionnaire completed by students.....	63
.....	64
.....	65
.....	66
.....	67
Appendix 2B: Microsoft questionnaire completed by teachers and specialists.....	68
.....	69
.....	70
.....	71
.....	72
Appendix 3: Interview with the Head of Primary pre intervention on March 17, 2026.....	73
Appendix 4: Interview with the Head of School on March 23, 2026.....	74
Appendix 5: Interview with the School Psychologist on March 25, 2026	74
Appendix 6: Interview with the PSHE teacher pre intervention on March 23, 2026	75
Appendix 7: Interview with the PSHE teacher post intervention on April 14, 2026.....	77
Appendix 8: Interview with the Head of Primary post intervention on April 30, 2026	78
Appendix 9: Intervention Design: Floor plan of the classroom before the changes; designed by Hannah Massaro.....	79
Appendix 10: Intervention Design: 3D model of the classroom before the changes; designed by Hannah Massaro.....	80

..... 81

..... 82

Appendix 11: Intervention Design: Floor plan of the classroom after the changes; designed by Hannah Massaro..... 83

Appendix 12: Intervention Design: 3D model of the classroom after the changes; designed by Hannah Massaro..... 84

..... 84

..... 85

Introduction

Scope and Impact of SEL in Connection to Classroom Design

Social-emotional learning (SEL) profoundly shapes students' development (World Health Organization, 2022). It is affecting their mental health, academic performance or progress in life and social relationships which is vulnerable to the long term. In recent years, however, a Zeitgeist shift has taken place with our relation to social-emotional wellbeing in shared society. Well-being is now taken into much more considerations than in prior decades. This is simultaneously shaping the long-term trend in understanding what it means to support vulnerability, emotional health and individual flourishing when educating (Ecclestone & Rawdin, 2020).

This cultural focus fits in with the greater wellness revolution that has changed how many cultures approach health. Transitioning from a model seeking to treat disease to one designed to actively make salient personal well-being in the physical, psychological, and emotional domains (BusinessNews Publishing, 2014). The wellness revolution also extends into education, in recognition of children's well-being highlighted through mandatory PSHE (Personal, Social, Health and Economic) education provision and health literacy-focused curricula with emotional goals (Kilgour et al., 2015).

The World Health Organization (2022) emphasizes the critical role of the environment in child and adolescent development, stating:

“The quality of the environment where children and adolescents grow up shapes their well-being and development. Early negative experiences in homes, schools, or digital spaces, such as exposure to violence, the mental illness of a parent or other caregiver, bullying and poverty,

increase the risk of mental illness” (para. 3). This underscores the importance of positive, supportive environments.

The increased focus on SEL coincides with the higher levels of anxiety, emotional regulation and social connection demand many students face. Markers such as individual well-being, academic performance and classroom participation, resilience and mental health impacts (World Health Organization, 2022; Ecclestone & Rawdin, 2020) are relevant problems. This is why supportive learning environments are the key to early intervention. To mitigate the chances of a negative trajectory, however, schools and educators can be proactive; classrooms can be purposefully designed to support emotional regulation and use positive social norms/expectations to foster belonging (Kilgour et al., 2015).

This means optimizing the whole room to address social and emotional learning, or SEL, outcomes. These approaches not only meet urgent emotional and social need, but they also help students engage more deeply in learning activities. It additionally also means less behavior problems and better starts to lifetime wellness. In an age where emotional flourishing is just as important, if not more so than cognitive development (Fang et al., 2022; World Health Organisation, 2022), aligning physical learning spaces with the ideals of social-emotional learning could provide educational and design solutions that lead to environments which actually foster the holistic child.

Historical and Contemporary Use of Non-Purpose-Built Buildings

Several schools in Europe, especially in the private sector, often find themselves operating buildings not originally designed or built for school use. This is reflective of a continuation of traditional practices as well as modern metropolitan life. That often leads to spaces that must be extensively redesigned to meet the demands of 21st century pedagogy and socio-emotional needs. Teaching occurred in pre-19th century buildings, including private houses and churches or other suitable room adaptations. Purpose-built school designs were only prevalent when mass public education systems expanded. This legacy persists today in a lot of private institutions, which place more importance on location, prestige and flexibility than the original architectural statement.

One such case is England, where many top private schools are sited in old country houses and large estates never intended as educational establishments. As Walford (2021) notes, dozens of elite public schools – including many boarding institutions with a long history linked to the major associations – have been founded in adapted country houses. The current article addresses how these historically important buildings add to the symbolic value and exclusivity of private schooling, while at the same time they perpetuate social inequality abstracting other non-educational architecture (Walford, 2021).

Such adaptations can also be observed throughout Europe, in this case conditioned by suburbanisation processes of the 21st century. For example, in the case of Budapest, school buildings tend to appear as reassessed constituents of new urban structures instead of fresh-built specialized venues. Kádek and Tamáska (2023) present case studies in Vác and Dunakeszi, two middle sized towns, to explore how schools manifest within suburban landscapes through real

estate conversion therefore being a product of the existing built environment moulded by urban forces.

Many private schools in Spain also start or function in non purpose built buildings rather than purpose-built designs. Long-term policy examples involving expansion and partial adaptation of existing structures face challenges are illustrated in cases as Betània-Patmos or Aula European School in Barcelona to manage expanded enrolment and evolving pedagogical needs (VIBRA, 2026). Focussing instead on site specific parameters, ownership changes and urban conditions (as opposed to new construction) these approaches often apply.

This is in contrast to the type of design that handles a high-performance facility, as emphasized by public education systems and EU-supported projects with their purpose-built model. Well-established educational buildings initiatives exhibit how purposeful design can ensure exemplary indoor environments are achievable (CORDIS, 2016). Purpose-built facilities typically allow for more effective integration of modern classroom layouts, natural light, acoustics, and flexible spaces. All of these are important factors for supporting not just social-emotional learning but learning in general.

However, in terms of optimizing social-emotional learning outcomes, we learn both the benefits and drawbacks of private schools repurposing existing buildings for other purposes. Although admirable charms of historic or redeveloped buildings can be attractive and have pleasing aesthetics, they frequently make it difficult to incorporate purposeful design elements. They may include flexible learning spaces, sensory-friendly areas or collaborative hubs. This

research is associated with increased emotional regulation, belonging, and well-being (Fang et al., 2022). Importantly, this reality supports the need for purposefully designed approaches for retrofitting existing school infrastructure and designs to align physical environments with SEL priorities as our world is awakening to the importance of more closely aligning the learning environment with mental and emotional needs that can impact children's development (World Health Organization, 2022).

Identified Problem and School Context

The previously mentioned focus of the present study will be a small, privately owned British international school located in Madrid, Spain (hereafter identified by the pseudonym 'school X'). Initially established as a company office rather than an education facility designed specifically purposes, this is not unusual for schools with privately and internationally taught curriculums (Walford, 2021). Hence, it only led to the classrooms where young learners would not be considered in their development as a person emotionally or socially. In particular, the absence of mobile structures, inadequate transportation and acoustic control, limited outdoor space as well as a lack of driven-in educational zoning still continue to present serious problems for children at both health and education issues. The Head of Primary noted that social-emotional learning “should always be revolving around... even if it’s like a little routine you do every morning, a visual thing that can help the kids identify emotions, it can help them connect this not only for like a 10-minute class but for the whole day” (Interview with Head of Primary pre intervention, personal communication, March 17, 2026).

A sense of institutional awareness from this participant that physical and pedagogical environments must align. This study aimed to produce stakeholder-informed evidence about how mixed Year 1–2 classroom design might be shaped to enhance SEL: belonging, emotional safety, self-regulation and empathy. Three guiding research questions were devised to operationalise this aim:

1. How might classroom zones be redesigned to optimally foster comfort, emotional safety, and connection, informed by the experiences of students and teachers?
2. In what ways could specific design elements such as layout, seating, lighting, and displays be iterated upon to support social-emotional learning?
3. What feasible design adjustments do students and teachers propose to enhance SEL in the classroom environment?

Its significance lies in being at the intersection of educational design and social-emotional learning within a narrowly focused case study: converted corporate office buildings into international school classrooms. Post COVID literature reflects that the time in a physical classroom is increasingly a determinant to help children return to social and emotional normalcy (Osher et al., 2020). At the same time, CASEL (2022) has solidified that SEL competencies such as self-awareness, self-management, social awareness, relationship skills and responsible decision-making are best developed as a whole school experience. This is including through its physical design. In summary, this study fills a gap in knowledge by translating these principles into a functional low-cost and transferable prototype for an overseas primary setting.

The report will be structured as follows: the Literature Review and Theoretical Framework section will position the research within previous studies; Methodology section provides an overview of DBR process and data collection steps; Findings sections presents a thorough analysis of both DBR cycle and stakeholder data; Discussion relates findings, theory, and practice together in one voice; Conclusion offers recommendations for future research and application.

Literature Review and Theoretical Framework

The Classroom as Third Teacher

Social-emotional learning has ceased to be a secondary activity to supporting performance in primary education. Domeier and Wiebe (2020) demonstrate the interrelation between classroom design, furniture flexibility, and zoning and the social and emotional well-being of students such that physical space is viewed as an operating lever of the safety, connectedness, and readiness to learn experienced by children. Hammond (2015) advises against failing to place a particular emphasis on cultural responsiveness, even a properly equipped room will cause the feeling of being threatened and reduce engagement. Therefore, classroom design is a strategic but unproductively studied facet of social-emotional learning especially in the international dimensions where the population of learners is very diverse and mobile.

The environment has been more and more characterized in pedagogical traditions in early years and primary education as a teaching companion than as an infrastructure. This metaphor has its roots in the Reggio Emilia philosophy where the environment is then conceptualised as the third teacher, who sits next to the child alongside the adult educator (Malaguzzi, 1994). Thornton and Brunton (2015) expound on this idea, explaining that Reggio-inspired classrooms have light, materials, and exhibits that are thoughtfully arranged to communicate a message of respect, belonging and agency. Rinaldi (2006) goes on to suggest that the environment should be able to communicate with the identities of the children and engage them in its surroundings and thus especially influential in a multicultural classroom whereby students can come in with very different cultural and linguistic backgrounds. The use of multilingual labels, student-produced displays and culturally diverse materials can significantly indicate inclusion in such settings.

According to Domeier and Wiebe (2020), the designs of spaces based more on logistical efficiency than on the former consequently favor able-bodied and confident learners, as opposed to others. This observation stands out especially at school X, which teachers all gave reports that every child of the Year 1/2 group had faced some form of SEL-related issues over time, be it the challenging behaviour, ADHD or attention and lack of self-regulation, and lack of empathy/social connection (Teacher Questionnaire, 2026). The classroom is not therefore a passive vessel but a social process that restricts or facilitates children to experience feelings of safety, their ability to control their emotions, and their ability to relate with their peers.

Theoretical Framework

The concept for the preliminary psychopedagogical and methodological basis of your research study is consist of several levels, however. Maslow (1943), and you find the hierarchy of needs at its core, arguing that safety and belonging are preconditions of cognitive engagement such as higher-order thinking. When a student's basic needs are dissatisfied, most notably the need for physical and emotional safety are unmet (due to lack of space, poorly defined spaces or culturally affirming material), schools cannot offer the conditions necessary for self-actualisation in the form of academic learning. The school psychologist of school X alluded to this model very obviously in her pre-intervention interview: "I think this is bringing me back to Maslow's hierarchy of needs: Once students are secure in their basic needs, they would respond better and reach their potential (Interview with School Psychologist, personal communication, March 25th, 2026). This reflects the theoretical alignment between Maslow's model and the targeted SEL outcomes in this case study.

The classroom redesign is guided pedagogically by a new take on Maslow, the third-teacher and Reggio Emilia (Malaguzzi, 1994; Thornton & Brunton, 2015). When the environment itself becomes a teacher, even where to place the calm corner, how exactly to position the seats and what should go on the walls all become pedagogical actions. In reframing the issue of classroom design as an exercise in educational intentionality and professional responsibility, it ceases to be a logistical concern.

The core five SEL competencies of CASEL (2022) self-awareness, self-management, social awareness, relationship, and responsible decision-making are the self-determined outcome framework of this paper. Environmental features can aid or weaken each competency. An example of scaffolding happens in the case of self-management where students have a quiet space to control emotions and resume learning in the community. Shared responsibility and collaboration in the form of social seating pods contribute to the development of social awareness and relationship skills. Student-created displays and culturally responsive visual content creates a sense of belonging as the foundational condition of well-being and engagement, as identified by Allen (2023).

This study is also based on the foundational principles of Universal Design of Learning (UDL; CAST, 2018). UDL supports multiple means of engagement, representation, and action/expression in the context of learning including the physical context. A classroom that follows UDL would mean making a calm environment, collaboration space and flexible furniture available to the entire classroom not just those officially deemed in need. This has relevance in a

global, inclusive classroom where neurodiverse learners and those undergoing transitional emotional (trauma) stages deserve equal access to the supportive spatial affordances.

Design Based Research and the Design Cycle

Methodologically, Bakker (2019) offers the conceptual framework of the Design-Based Research (DBR) approach of this study. DBR is typified by repetitive analysis, design, practice, and reflection, carried out in real educational contexts, and aimed at collaborative generation of design principles with practitioners. As Bakker (2019) insists, DBR is not about whether an intervention works or not but about the reasons and ways in which it works, thus creating theory-based knowledge that can be applied to other situations. This commitment to epistemology is especially relevant to a project that has an unusual physical location, namely a corporate building converted into a school, where it is not so easy to form generalisations because of the peculiarities of spatial affordances and constraints.

Wellington (2015) emphasizes that methodological rigour and reflexivity are crucial components of educational research, especially in qualitative and mixed methods research. His message to researchers to be open on their positionality and their decisions of the data collection tools guide how the researcher handled this research where he was both a student intern, a design agent and a data collector. This multi-role role positioning brought with it both exclusive access and bias possibilities as in the Methodology section.

Previous studies concerning classroom set up and learning outcomes have provided a substantial evidence base for this. Barrett et al. (2015) found potential for classroom physical features (naturalness [air quality, light, temperature], individualisation and the right stimulation

explained 16% variation in academic progress over a year, up to an effect size of 1 as part of one stimulus factor impact. Explain this more fully: in their large-scale meta-analyses Domitrovich et al. (2017). By contrast, Weissberg et al. (2011) found that the most efficacious SEL programmes are those which operate at a school-wide climate level, as opposed to as discrete lessons. These results also support the implementation of SEL as part of the regular physical classroom, rather than as a distinct PSHE lesson.

This study will fill gaps about the gap of applied DBR research related to low-cost, co-designed classroom contexts in small international schools housed in non-purpose-built facilities. Classroom design research is largely confined to arguably contrived, well-resourced conditions within national education systems, rendering the findings less generalizable to the unique constraints of an independent International school (McKenney and Reeves 2018). Also, this study was conducted at school X with its re-designed corporate structure, multilingual students and a low budget design constraint; hence contributing to the contextual links of the developed prototype that can be directly employed into similar contexts.

The design principles at play in this intervention stem from and are informed by all strands of the CASEL (2022) intervention framework discussed above. To start with, intentional zoning create defined areas of particular emotional/social functions: quiet zones needs to be for self-regulating emotion; common pods, supporting empathy and relationships; open-ended traffic area, slowing inter-personal stress (Thornton & Brunton 2015). Second, in the displays and materials those he/she would encounter within a culturally responsive classroom (Hammond, 2015) -- should affirm diverse student identity so that the student is emotionally safe. Third, movable chairs that

can be easily reconfigured and lights fitted with outlets to power devices accommodate varying emotional states (e.g. Fourth, design sustainability to ensure that any changes can be sustained with the existing school resources; this point as well is critical because school leadership have already embraced the idea that budget constraints will hinder greatness (Interview with Head of School, personal communication, March 23 2026).

Key Words

Classroom design: The purposeful placement and structure of physical objects in a learning space, such as seating, zoning, lighting, displays, access to materials, etc., to facilitate pedagogical and social objectives.

Social-emotional learning (SEL): Children and adults achieve a set of fundamental social, emotional, and relational capabilities, such as self-awareness, self-management, social awareness, building relationships, and responsible decision-making (CASEL, 2022).

Design-Based Research (DBR): A research approach that is both iterative and practice-based, where both theoretical understanding and empirical knowledge are generated by cycles of design, implementation, evaluation and revision in a natural education environment (Bakker, 2019).

Third teacher: This is an idea inspired by a Reggio Emilia approach where the physical environment remains an active and pedagogical partner with the child and the adult educator (Malaguzzi, 1994).

International primary education: Early years and primary schooling delivered in international schools, characterised by diverse, multinational student and staff populations, frequent student transitions, and curriculum frameworks designed for global mobility.

Belonging: The subjective feeling of being accepted, cherished and fitting into a social group; a prerequisite to well-being and academic involvement (Allen, 2023; Maslow, 1943).

Self-regulation: The ability to engage in control of emotional responses, impulses and behaviours in goal-oriented fashion; a fundamental SEL competency especially subject to environmental scaffolding.

Methodology

Research Design

The overarching methodological framework of this research was Design-Based Research (DBR), as outlined by Bakker (2019). DBR outbenchers interventions aimed at addressing both real-world practical problems of situated contexts, and for developing transposable design concepts. Unlike the experimental research design dynamics where variables are isolated and controlled, DBR recognizes that real classrooms consist of complex, contextual settings, which is appropriate for this specific international school context with its space limitations and heterogeneous learner cohort. The current project employed a DBR cycle with four repetition steps aligned with Design Thinking (Brown, 2008): (1) Empathise and define, (2) ideate, (3) prototype, and (4) test and reflect. These were adopted over nine weeks of gradual teaching practice and will be elaborated on in the Findings section.

Data collection remains qualitative and participatory throughout, in accordance with the more critical emphasis on situational knowledge; Wellington (2015) speaks of this in terms of research into education. Qualitative techniques are essential, for example to enable the capturing of subtle stakeholder attitudes towards emotional feeling in the classroom setting, which would be impossible quantitatively. Where a structured instrument such as a Microsoft Forms questionnaire was implemented, the intent was to triangulate and contextualise rather than generate statistically generalisable results.

Participants and Context

Research was undertaken at school X located in Madrid, Spain which is a small private British international school with an enrolment of around 60 pupils between Nursery and Year 6. The building of the school used to be a corporate office which was not constructed to be used as a school building. This source has certain structural drawbacks: classrooms are quite small to accommodate the number of pupils they are designed to accommodate, there is a lack of outdoors areas, and the rooms are not built in manner typical of school architecture, with dedicated separating spaces or adjustable lighting.

Thirteen children in a mixed Year 1/2 class (six Year 1 students (although one did not give informed consent) with codes Y1-01-Y1-06 but not Y1-03) and seven Year 2 students (Y2-01-Y2-07) formed the core group of participants. The children were between 5-7 years of age. The school was representative of the international population of the school in general, and the children in the class were of various nationalities and languages. The heterogeneous classroom composition was complicated by the mixed-age observation, as there was a wide range of development in this group.

There were four important informants as the adults and those were the Head of School, the Head of Primary, the PSHE (Personal, Social, Health and Economic Education) teacher that was also a co-intern at the school, and the educational psychologist of the school. These participants were purposely selected (Wellington, 2015) due to their varied professional viewpoints on the school culture, policies, needs of learners, and teaching environment. One other eight teaching and support staff was included in an online questionnaire as a Microsoft Forms, consisting of ten items.

Class teachers, co-teachers, specialists teachers and the school secretary also responded to this questionnaire.

Data Collection Methods

Data was collected using a range of tools that corresponded to various phases of the DBR cycle and several stakeholder types. This mixture method of research allowed triangulation as well as ensuring the inclusion of adults and children in the design process.

Semi-structured interviews with school leadership and specialist staff

Semi-structured interviews with the school leadership team and specialist staff were conducted both pre intervention (before holidays) and post intervention (after the holidays). Six semi-structured interviews: Head of Primary (before intervention on March 30, 2026 and post the intervention on April 17, 2026); Head of School (before the intervention, March 23, 2026); teacher of PSHE (before the intervention, March 23, 2026), teacher of PSHE post-intervention: after holidays (April 14, 2026). In addition, the school psychologist (pre-intervention on March 25, 2026) was interviewed. Student and teacher interview questions were designed to elicit perspectives regarding SEL within the school context, perceived affordances and constraints of current classroom design, potential for redesign in the resource limitations of the school as well as (pre-intervention) perceptions around student behaviours and emotional regulation versus educator reported changes to these parameters post intervention). The interviews were performed audio-recorded, thematically analysed. There were prepared sample consent forms for the teachers who were going to be interviewed prior to data collection and those who were doing the questionnaire. As in the report, pseudonyms and role descriptors have been used to protect participants identities of children and teaching staff.

Teacher questionnaire Targets: Microsoft Forms

Eight members of the teaching and support staff at school X received a structured questionnaire digitally in Microsoft Forms. The tool covered the attitudes towards the correlation of classroom design with SEL, ratings of existing design features, observation of SEL-related issues in the Year 1200 classroom, and suggested improvements to the design. Seven out of eight respondents said that they were currently teaching at school X, with four stating they are or co-teaching in the mixed Year 1/2 classroom of Year 1. The questionnaire had a duration span of 24 days with an average case of 22 minutes and 37 seconds to complete. The consent was also considered in the final question: all the eight respondents agreed that they had read and signed the Teacher Consent Form, which was written by the researcher. The questionnaire was used as a needs assessment and a data triangulation tool of the interview data.

Student baseline questionnaire based on Microsoft Forms

Year 1/2 students (N = 12; 5–7 years old) acted as pre-intervention respondents, each completing a semi-structured child-friendly version of a Microsoft Forms questionnaire adapted for children. The researcher provided this tool and it was prototyped through verbal competition using a scribe, with respect for UDL principles of providing accessibility to all students regardless of their literacy skills (CAST, 2018). Dependent variables included (i) emotional thermometer at the time of completion (angry, frustrated, worried, sad, calm, happy); (ii) feeling caring in the classroom; (iii) feeling safe and comfortable; the children own thoughts perceptions on how friends feel; preferred working situations (alone or group work [small groups were flexible]); and lighting and displays as observations on climate. The questionnaire was deployed both qualitatively (40 days) and in a well-structured manner. Parental consent was obtained from all twelve children who were involved using a modified sample explanation of what research means using age-appropriate

assent terminology. Parents gave their consent through the consent form while children gave their consent verbally.

Drawings made by children: classroom now and dream classroom

The students were also asked to draw their own classroom (pre intervention) and their dream classroom in a PSHE lesson, this was a non-verbal elicitation method designed to tap into emotional and aesthetic desires that children may not yet articulate with language. Drawing-based data collection within the field of education has been recognized as an inclusive and developmentally appropriate practice which was able to elicit insider (or self) understandings of children's worlds (Wellington, 2015). The researcher considered these drawings to be representative of an array of shared visual commonalities (e.g. plants, soft lighting and warm corners, family photographs), cross referencing their use against the verbal account made by children and documented by the researcher.

Work on Garland (class bunting activity) in a group

After the interpretation of the drawings of the dream classroom of children, the co-creation activity was organized, during which the students worked on the design of a class Garland (an ornament in the form of bunting garland). The activity was a design consultation and a belonging-building intervention. The children also adorned their own triangular shaped panels using their own images, artwork and symbols depicting their identity and desirability in the classrooms. These boards were put together into the Garland and hung over the ceiling in the classroom to become a very visible artefact of agency and ownership among students. The work in progress of children and photographs of the finished Garland were photographed and will be analyzed.

Before-and-after classroom photographs

Pictures of the classroom in the state before and after the physical intervention were taken to present a physical evidence of the design changes. Pictures were taken of seats, zoning factors, light setup, the tranquil corner, the portable material trolley, the affirmation displays, the family presentation boards and the Garland. These images were included in the prototype documentation and they served as a foundation to 3D modelling the classroom in each state.

Data Analysis Procedures

Inductive thematic analysis approach was also adopted to analyse qualitative data (interviews and open-ended questionnaire answers) gathered (Wellington, 2015). Interview transcripts were coded line by line, with codes clustered into themes relating to the key SEL outcomes targeted by the study: belonging, emotional safety, self-regulation, empathy, and confidence. Themes of constraints (space, budget, school culture) and design affordances were also considered. The PSHE teacher pre- and post-intervention interviews were directly compared to reveal observed behavioural changes that could be attributed to the design changes. The data of the questionnaires compiled through Microsoft Forms tools were analyzed descriptively, and frequencies and per centages of the responses given on the Likert-scale questions and word clouds and response summaries were used when the open questions were answered. Children drawings were reviewed on the appearance of repetitive visual themes and the Garland activity was seen as a co-design artefact at which the content of the artefact was used to inform the final prototype.

Ethical Considerations

This work was done within the framework of the ethical standards of the British Educational Research Association (BERA, 2018). All adult participants were informed about the research before data gathering and provided informed consent, teacher consent forms outlined how participation was voluntary and that these participants could withdraw any time without penalty, how data would be anonymised, and how data would be stored in password-secured factories, and how data would be used in the report and in potential academic presentation or publication. All children whose data was a part of the study had their consent provided by their parents with age-appropriate language being used in the consent documentation. Verbal assent explanations based on the children stage of development were also provided and the right not to participate was acknowledged (Y1-03 did not consent and has not been included in the dataset). In order to counteract the power disproportion of the researcher acting as the student teacher and researcher the child-led elicitation tasks were devised to be non-leading and at all times emotional safety during the data collection process was a priority. The study was done upon consent and permission of the school principle and mentor. To maintain anonymity, both the school and all participants have been made anonymous throughout the study, and student data were assigned unique identifiers for coding.

Researcher Positionality

The research position of the researcher in this study was rather multifaceted: she was also a fourth-year student teacher in the area of the international teaching practice, a researcher, and a principal design agent of the classroom changes. This status provided privileged access to the school community members, everyday life of children, and the views of the staff, which aligns with participatory ethos of DBR (Bakker, 2019). But it also created the risk of confirmation bias -

especially the tendency to interpret post-intervention data in a way that justified the design decisions formed up to that point. To deal with this, the researcher attempted to disconfirm the results of the research by following interviews, transcribing the occurrence of raw data in an open and transparent nature and tapping the structured questionnaire as a separate triangulation source. The researcher also kept reflexive research journal during the nine weeks which he used to record assumptions, surprises and methodological choices.

Universal Design Learning Principles

The research design and intervention used UDL principles in the classroom (CAST, 2018). Concerning research design, avenues of reciprocal engagement were offered through drawing, online questionnaire, face to face discussion and co-creating activity – ensuring that no one child was disadvantaged by barriers in literacy or communication simulation. In terms of the intervention in the classroom, all of the design changes can be understood to provide a number of ways for children to interact with their learning environment; always available as an option, having access to a quiet corner tent meant that children with anxiety or neurodevelopmental needs had a place they could withdraw from class when they needed it designated as their own (Kearney, 2009); using bags/boxes on wheels provided movable materials which kept all children engaged with this part of their learning environment without having to mediate through the teacher; and having clearly designated seating gave continued predictability and structure – two very important factors for young children who may also be experiencing anxiety or other types neurodevelopmental challenge.

Findings

Design-Based Research Cycle Overview

This research paper is organized according to the 4 stages of the DBR cycle (Bakker, 2019): (1) Empathise and Define, (2) Ideate and Co-Design, (3) Prototype, and (4) Test and Reflect. At each of these stages various instruments were taken and their data collectively processed and fed into the next design decisions. This cyclicity of the process demonstrates the principle underpinning the DBR that interventions do not have a priori coding, but instead respond to the emerging evidence.

Phase 1: Empathise and Define

The initial stage, which would be completed within Weeks 1 and 2 of the internship, was the construction of an overall picture of the existing classroom setting and the impact that it has on the SEL of students. Observations of classroom routines during the physical activity of children in a classroom with non-participants indicated some recurring challenges as follows: children often have to bump and push each other when traveling between the carpet and tables as there is not enough space between them; several students are competing over a shared resource (scissors, pencils, glue sticks and others) which causes interpersonal conflict; and a quiet corner area is not defined and is underused (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Classroom environment before intervention

The current seating was not determined by specific seats that individual children were to occupy, and the PSHE teacher realized that led to fights over chairs and fostered a sense of social unrest

(Interview with PSHE Teacher pre intervention, personal communication, March 23, 2026) (see Figure 2 and 3).

Figure 2. Initial classroom layout and seating arrangement

Figure 3. Teacher desk and whiteboard

The student baseline questionnaire showed that out of twelve respondents; six individuals said they felt calm during the survey, four said they felt happy, one individual was said to be angry and one was said to be worried at the moment of the survey (see Figure 4)

Figure 4. Student emotional baseline questionnaire result

When children were asked what their social environment and interpersonal factors are that make me feel safe in the classroom, responses ranged from I feel safe because of my teacher and my friends to Sometimes I feel scared because Manuel wants to fight. Most children (75% of whichever day they work) said both working individually and in groups best suited them, but the flexibility of space is vital for both; In this way, kids clustered quite a bit within the kind of classroom lighting they felt was too brilliant; once more, it mirrored the industrial-feel of their corporate constructing this fluorescent workplace lighting not designed to encourage child consolation, solely children productiveness.

Supportive evidence was gained via the teacher questionnaire. All the eight respondents (100% all) agreed or strongly agreed that classroom design is a key influencing factor and provision of SEL outcomes, while lesson proforma were perceived as equally impacting on achieving an appropriate environment being found among all respondents. In the eyes of teachers, outcome of SEL promoted by design as a whole was pressed for rating, with an outcome sense of

belonging and lowest rank confidence suggesting that other than some relational factors in the outcomes there are no indicators as self-efficacy help. You needed zsome specific types of indoor-outdoor centers such as open ended response calm corner self regulation better displays materials being stock ed age appropriate made accessible.

The triangulation on leadership level consisted of semi-structured interviews with Head of School, Head of Primary and school psychologist. Even the Head of School had to concede that at a school-building and overcrowded classes are "that are simply incompatible" with children crowded together wrestling over space and interaction in harmony (Interview with Head of School, personal communication, March 23, 2026). When the school psychologist used Maslow (1943) to describe this relationship between physical environment and SEL outcomes, he cited a hierarchy of needs and said that if a student has five safety needs met, he or she participates more in learning. The Head of Primary noted the significance of visual routine and emotional anchors in a classroom, specifically among new international students who must experience transitions: a student who learns that they are in a safe space. will recover [academically] because they will be safe, they will be ready to learn (Interview with Head of Primary pre intervention, March 17, personal communication, 2026). The children drawings of their current classroom mostly covered functional features-desks, interactive white board, the bulletin board, and very limited reflection on emotional support parts. In contrast, their depictions of an ideal classroom all had the same motifs: warm and dark lighting (fairy lights or lamps), soft seating (beanbags or laydown zones), plants and natural objects, muted colour palettes, personal photos/ family photos on the wall and special areas to relax. The following principles of design, centered around the child, constituted

the core lessons informing later phases of ideation and prototyping and fulfilled the DBR commitment to participatory co-design (Bakker, 2019).

Phase 2: Ideate and Co-Design

The researcher generalised a range of design principles based on the empathy data to guide the intervention. These included: (a) establish unique zones around various emotional and social functions; (b) have individualized personal space of children in the classroom; (c) have easy access of all daily items to children; (d) provide supportive and warm supplementary light to soften the lighting environment; (e) provide confirming student-centred visual displays that identify who children are; (f) have a designated semi-enclosed quiet area to regulate emotions.

In this phase, the Garland co-design activity took place. Students covered personal triangular panels with self-portraits, images and personal artwork of cultural and familial background. The process of shared creating the bunting garland was itself a design consultation process (establishing the children preference of identity-affirming, personalised items in the classroom), and a form of belonging-building intervention, since the collaborative act of making the garland meant that children had to listen to others, appreciate, and celebrate others. The Garland, which had been finished, hung on the ceiling of the classroom, and in one move the appearance of the classroom was completely changed and this piece becomes a permanent part of the collective identity of the classes.

Figure 4. Classroom Garland final display

All design principles were consulted with the school teachers and the PSHE teacher to make sure that they are possible within the budget and space constraints of the school. The Head of Primary clarified that the school already had the storage where they could find some of the materials, and the researcher obtained other cheap supplies (a tiny tent with the quiet corner and a trolley with IKEA-style design which were already possessed by the school). No major monetary cost was made and the sustainability design principle, as well as the need of the school leadership to ensure a change, are met since it will fall within the current resource parameters.

Phase 3: Prototype

The physical classroom itself was redesigned over the school holidays (March 30 – April 10), when children returned they found an entirely transformed physical environment to the one which had been established before. Its initial configuration put children at random tables, with no assigned seats, replaced by a semi-peripheral layout through the placement of oval tables near walls. Each child received a name tag, which was assigned to a fixed number of one chair. The change was made because the seating issue was the most common issue, and with a consistent space identity each child could have a reliable place in the classroom (see Figure 5).

Figure 5. New seating arrangements

Zoning. The classroom has been split into three parts of the functional areas: a collaborative learning area (the tables and chairs area), a whole-class gathering area (the carpet area, which is enhanced with individual pink circle floor mats and a dark circle rug) and a peaceful corner area. Bright visual and physical divisions between areas were created to help children to grasp the spatial grammar in the room (see Figure 6 and 7).

Figure 6. Visible zoning of the classroom

Figure 7. Visible zoning of the classroom

Calm corner. A small tent was fixed in a corner of the classroom, equipped with soft cushions, a calm-down toy (a snake), books and other quiet activities. Space was presented to children in this area specifically as a self-regulatory area. A mirror with positive affirmations were printed was placed close by, which allowed children to self-reflect and self-encourage themselves before being allowed back into the learning community (see Figure 8, 9 and 10).

Figure 8. Calm corner

Figure 9. Mirrors with affirmations

Figure 10. Calming Corner with self-regulation strategies

Material accessibility. Each child was given individual cups with their pencils, scissors, and other personal stationery, which removed the conflicts of shared resources in Phase 1. An old trolley was reused to store colouring pencils and water bottles so that this could make the resources available independently without having to mediate with the teacher (see Figure 11).

Figure 11. Student's cups with name tags

Lighting adjustment. Existing window blinds were organized to dim overhead fluorescent lights where there was focused work and during times of calm. The Garland (its warm bunting and string lights) also served to give a softer background aesthetic (see Figure 12)

Figure 12. Fairy lights with changing colors

Visual setting and displays. The bulletin boards were reworked to have a specific area of student created work in the Garland project, family photographs shared by children and mirrors with positive affirmation. The desk of the teacher was reconfigured to be conveniently placed and the first-order learning area was decluttered to minimize visual stimulation (see Figure 6 and 13).

Figure 13. Teacher materials and desk

Design and Rationale for 3D Modelling as an Intervention Tool

To support the visualisation and communication of the intervention, two comparative 3D classroom models (pre- and post-implementation) were designed using Planner 5D (Planner 5D, n.d.). The decision to use 3D modelling was grounded in the need for a flexible and accessible tool that could make spatial changes visible to a broad audience, including teachers, leadership, and students. While highlight measures of layout, and behaviour in regard to the area is addressed with purely textual or 2D representations, it has been shown that viewers can perceive layout, movement and zoning more intuitive using 3D models which has some implications for our understanding of how physical environments relate to behaviour (Gosling et al., 2013). Alternative Tools Needed Several alternative tools had been considered: Minecraft, SketchUp and some higher-end programmes such as AutoCAD, even the idea of a physical model; dollhouse-style. But these solutions either needed a lot of upfront knowledge, lots of hours or were slow in getting to an iterative conclusion. Planner 5D (Massaro a, 2026) and (Massaro b, 2026) was eventually chosen as it required no advanced technical skills yet still provide a detailed and accurate visual representation of the classroom, that could be easily updateable. It links to the third teacher idea that "Intentionality must be implemented, if it is not apparent or interpretable by stakeholders, then it could also be described as indiscriminate." (Brown, 2020) This was important because the selected tool facilitated quick prototyping throughout the DBR cycle but also allowed for a rich description of design so that it remained theoretically informed and practically meaningful.

Impact of Spatial Redesign on Student Behaviour and Learning

The virtual version of this intervention was tested among teaching staff through a semi-structured interview with the Head of Primary post intervention (personal communication, April 30, 2026). When presented with the comparative 3D models (pre- and post-intervention), she emphasised that the redesign extended beyond aesthetics, noting that “it shows that it’s done to improve the way the kids behave... the kids listen and work” (personal communication, April 30, 2026). She identified spatial reorganisation, particularly the peripheral table layout and increased central space as a key factor in reducing distraction and enhancing focus. This finding reflects principles from environmental psychology, which suggest that the design of interior spaces directly influences behaviour, movement, and social interaction (Gosling et al., 2013). The 3D models made these relationships visible, allowing stakeholders to clearly interpret how zoning, accessibility, and movement pathways contributed to improved Social-Emotional Learning (SEL) outcomes

Phase 4: Reflect and Test

When the children returned to school after a school break, the PSHE teacher was re-interviewed to record her observations about how the students reacted to the redesigned classroom and how she noticed any change of behaviour in students. Its particularity made her story striking: They were super surprised. They even got really calm, I think, just seeing it. They were so surprised that they didn’t talk or they just, wow. She also observed how children assimilated the new rules of space quickly, and would automatically find their own carpet time floor mats, without having to be reminded: I think it was Aadhit or somebody, he said at once, we must take our little mats.

The shift towards carpet in the forms of tables was termed as being more peaceful as the given seating eliminated any type of competition, and the use of shared pencils was minimized, which minimized interpersonal conflict on work hours (Interview with PSHE Teacher post intervention, personal communication, April 14, 2026).

The PSHE teacher justified these changes by appealing to a combination of design factors, especially the higher predictability: They know where they have to get which chair and they know their cup and that makes them behave better. She also described what she called the "quiet spot" as preventive, not a punishment—as when we sensed one of the children nearby was becoming somewhat frisky. We may send that child away in the tent, we might discover that child needs to settle down a bit. For example, one student, John, was just using the calm-down snake on his own, and the toy appeared to help him relax without adult assistance.

If theoretical predictions are to be acted upon, then the post intervention observations when compared in this framework for the study, should adhere to said principles. After the children pass through the requirements predictability and physical safety as introduced in Maslow's (1943) hierarchy of needs, to reinforce these own with clear spatial producing bearing in mind individual spaces and quiet zones with intimate characters their possibilities will act prosocial behaviour later than learning. Resilience is one of the SEL competencies identified by CASEL (2022), and a Calm Corner directly embodies this postulate as well. This finding from the PSHE teacher that less effective emotional regulation had an indirect positive impact on children via more beneficial learning experiences is therefore consistent with the findings of Domitrovich et al. (2017).

3D Modelling as a Tool for Scalable Pedagogical Change and Teacher Professional Development

Beyond evaluating the intervention, the 3D modelling tool (Massaro c, 2026) demonstrated strong potential as a scalable instrument for critical change within the school context. Maria highlighted its practical value, explaining that “it helps visualize the space... teachers [can] make a draft or put their ideas into place” and use it to communicate ideas more effectively (Interview with Head of Primary post intervention,, personal communication, April 30, 2026). The Head of Primary also proposed that these types of models could help junior teachers by creating a consistent model for building the classroom/SEL principles into conscientious design, from day one. This relates to the idea that the classroom is the "third teacher where purposeful space influences both learning and feeling experiences (Brown, 2020). Crucially, the nature of the models as comparisons allowed for stakeholders to know that they could "see the difference" between environments (Interview with Head of Primary post intervention, personal communication 30 April 2026), and further, not only represented change but were themselves also a tool within design-based research cycling from reflexivity.

Discussion

Classroom Environment as a Tool for SEL Development

The classroom is positioned as a prototype for bettering SEL in this practical research. Innovation enriches both shorter term council needs addressed in an international context in Y1-2 through leveraging insider knowledge and school resources by stakeholders to increase belonging and emotional safety, but also longer term learning derived from rationalizing spatial design via empathic analysis and co-creation for more transferable education practice. These findings align with Malaguzzi's (1994) and Thornton and Brunton's (2015) proposed third-teacher model that emphasizes a silent yet impactful teacher role of environment.

Triangulation and Validity of Findings

What is especially conspicuous is the considerable overlap of evidence provided by different data sources. Inadequate zoning, inadequate access to material, too few places for children to rest and excessive bright overhead lighting were similar design weaknesses of the school identified by teachers, school administration and children themselves that signal a weak idea as a common one score in many schools. The overlap also improves the significance of the findings and suitability of the design response (Wellington, 2015).

Spatial Predictability and Self-Regulation

The most comprehensive finding is the correlation between spatial predictability and children emotional self-regulation. The configuration of cups inserted into layers of the space separated objects; and pre-defined zones structured a grammar for how to use space, which kids trained in reading the spaces. This observation is also relevant to the argument of Osher et al.

(2020) asserts that relationships and contexts including the physical environment are pivotal to human development, and that stable and predictable environments provide the foundation of the capacity of humans for self-regulation and social interaction. The quiet spot, in particular, was a physical manifestation of the self-management competency of CASEL (2022) and it provided an actual spatial resource for what was previously only verbal descriptions of emotional regulation processes.

Emotional Impact of the Redesigned Environment

The unexpected findings following the completion of the redesigned classroom also included an immediate positive affective response among children towards the redesigned classroom. The PSHE teacher who was telling how children walked into the room and how calm they were. This means that all the visual and spatial accumulative influence of gentle light, pleasant Garland; free spaces; personal details were qualitatively new atmosphere in which children found themselves safer and more comfortable with respect to the previous arrangement. This echoes the conclusion reached by Barrett et al. as well (2015), find that interventions with multi-dimensional classroom contexts (high on naturalness, individualisation, and stimulation) are significantly more effective than if one of these variables were to be manipulated alone.

Practical Implications for Low-Cost Classroom Design

Practical implications are important. The prototype shows that there is sufficient evidence-based cost-efficient classroom SEL improvement that can be implemented at minimal cost by using available school resources - this is especially true with a number of small, independent international schools that have limited financial resources. The Head of School made it clear that budget was a limiting aspect at school X (Interview with Head of School, personal communication,

2026), and that the success of the design cycle with constraining factors implies that the concepts of the prototype can be applied to schools with comparable constraints. The 3D pre-and post-models designed within the scope of this project provide a visually transferable resource which can guide school leaders and teachers to comprehend and apply the design principles to the school settings.

Theoretical contributions relate to the addition to DBR international and educational literature. According to McKenney and Reeves (2018) in their review article, the most valuable examples of DBR research are those that result in local instruction theories that can be generalizable but rooted within a certain context. Intentional zoning, personal spatial identity and access to materials; cultural responsiveness; calm—to name a few of the design principles employed in this study—also fit the bill. They are context-specific, (school X based), but can be framed in terms that will potentially apply to any early years or primary school where the physical environment has not been purposefully designed in a goal-oriented manner to SEL.

The bar graphs qualitative research results correspond well with the study by Barrett et al. (2015) of the classroom design in large-scale settings, which found naturalness, individualisation, and relevant stimulation to be the three most significant physical dimensions according to the implications of pupil progress. The prototype created at the school X met the three dimensions: naturalness enhanced through the adjusted lighting and introduction of the Garland; individualisation offered by the named seating and personal material cups; and minimal overstimulation offered by the calm corner to children with self-regulation requirement. The

overlap between this small-scale DBR and Barrett et al. (2015) quantitative results indicate that the findings can be confidently transferred to the high-scale and methodology-different context. Surprisingly, there was the rate and intensity of behaviour adjustment in children. What had taken students some time to learn in a single session after their holiday, including learning their floor mats spontaneously and switching between zones with significantly reduced conflict, was the spatial grammar of the redesigned room. This implies that young children are very sensitive to spatial information and that the relatively small design modifications that involve low cost can change behavioural patterns relatively quickly in the event that there is consistency and coherence in the changes made. This observation was not envisaged in the design and contributes complexity to the literature at hand, which has tended to conceptualize environmental change as an incremental process that takes a long time to adapt.

With respect to teacher-training, the research paper in this study outlines the importance of incorporating classroom design into initial teacher education programmes (teacher training), specifically those courses that prepare teachers to work in international environments. Student teachers are also advantageous by having represented guidelines of applying SEL theory to spatial decisions. Specifically, for the policy of international school design it asserts the need to develop evaluation mechanisms that determine whether existing or newly procured premises are appropriately proportioned in terms of educational zoning, acoustics, lighting flexibility and provision of emotional support environments within which children may be located in this case study.

Conclusions

This paper has showed that careful redesigning of the classroom, based on a stakeholder-best-informed plan, and attentive of resources, can result in quantifiable gains to the social-emotional learning climate of an international primary classroom taught by a mixture of Year 1 and 2 pupils. The DBR cycle created a prototype that could be replicated in other locations and included six major design modifications such as seating reconfiguration with named places, flexible zoning, a calm corner, accessible materials, adjusted lighting and culturally responsive displays that were based on the articulated needs of children, the professional knowledge of teachers and leadership views. The PSHE teacher-reported after intervention evidence reflected less interpersonal conflict, a more fluid transition, and more autonomous levels of self-regulation and an apparent change in the classroom environment.

What is important about this research is that it shows that the physical environment is not a given background to learning, but a dynamic pedagogical agent that can be constantly improved. It is no luxury but a necessity especially in the case of international schools with their mobile student populations, their heterogeneity of cultural identities and often non-purpose-built buildings to meet them. The need to be safe and to belong is captured in the evocation of hierarchy by Maslow (1943) through the school psychologist: the circumstances under which children flourish in both academic and social arenas is unavailable to students until they are safe and belong.

Future research recommendations take on the following form (a) the design principles should be tested by a longitudinal follow-up study on whether the observed behavioural changes will be maintained over an academic year (b) the design should be tested across several classrooms

within the same school or network to test the generalizability of the design principles (c) the effect of classroom redesign could be investigated on specific subgroups of children, especially neurodiverse learners and newly arrived international.

Limitations

There are some limitations on the conclusions that can be made out of this study. To begin with, the sample size is relatively small; twelve children and eight respondent teachers results do not allow the test results to be statistically generalised. The study can be considered more of an in-depth, contextual, case study, but not a well-representative research study. Second, the length of the internship (nine weeks) implied that the post-intervention testing period was not lengthy; the after-interview with the PSHE teacher took place days after the children came back without holiday and it was hard to tell the immediate effect of the new environment on the children as well as the beneficial impact that lasted. Third, the dual role of the researcher as student teacher and design agent projected the possibility of confirmation bias in interpreting the data, in spite of the reflexive strategies that were used. Fourth, physical aspects of the building, especially lack of dedicated outdoors space, the fixed overhead fluorescent lighting which could not be removed were the possible factors that constrained the extent of design changes possible. Fifth, a lack of standardised SEL assessment tools resulting in the use of self-report and observation data makes claims about SEL outcome improvements tentative and qualitative. Further studies using validated SEL instruments to study the principles of the design used in the present study in a pre-post study would lend more weight to the evidence that was discovered in this study.

References

- Allen, K. A. (2023). *The psychology of belonging*. Routledge.
- Bakker, A. (2019). *Design research in education: A practical guide for early career researchers*. Routledge.
- Barrett, P., Davies, F., Zhang, Y., & Barrett, L. (2015). The impact of classroom design on pupils' learning: Final results of a holistic, multi-level analysis. *Building and Environment*, 89, 118–133. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2015.02.013>
- British Educational Research Association. (2018). *Ethical guidelines for educational research* (4th ed.). BERA. <https://www.bera.ac.uk/publication/ethical-guidelines-for-educational-research-2018>
- Brown, M. F. (2020). *The third teacher: An analysis of aesthetic and intentionality of space in the classroom*.
- BusinessNews Publishing. (2014). *Summary: The wellness revolution*. Primento.
- CAST. (2018). *Universal design for learning guidelines version 2.2*. CAST. <http://udlguidelines.cast.org>
- Collaborative for Academic, Social, and Emotional Learning. (2022). *What is the CASEL framework?* <https://casel.org/fundamentals-of-sel/what-is-the-casel-framework/>
- CORDIS. (2016, February 11). *Constructing energy efficient schools for the future*. European Commission. <https://cordis.europa.eu/article/id/118805-constructing-energy-efficient-schools-for-the-future>
- Domeier, M., & Wiebe, S. (2020). Spaces that speak: Classroom design and social-emotional learning in early years settings. *Journal of Early Childhood Education*, 48(3), 221–235.

Domitrovich, C. E., Durlak, J. A., Staley, K. C., & Weissberg, R. P. (2017). Social-emotional competence: An essential factor for promoting positive adjustment and reducing risk in school children. *Child Development*, 88(2), 408–416. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cdev.12739>

Durlak, J. A., Weissberg, R. P., Dymnicki, A. B., Taylor, R. D., & Schellinger, K. B. (2011). The impact of enhancing students' social and emotional learning: A meta-analysis of school-based universal interventions. *Child Development*, 82(1), 405–432. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8624.2010.01564.x>

Ecclestone, K., & Rawdin, C. (2020). Reinforcing the 'diminished' subject? The implications of the 'vulnerability zeitgeist' for well-being in educational settings. In *Social and emotional learning* (pp. 103–119). Routledge.

Fang, Y., Lou, X., & Lu, J. (2022). A review of research on the impact of the classroom physical environment on schoolchildren's health. *Journal of Building Engineering*, 65. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S235271022201436X>

Gosling, S. D., Gifford, R., & McCunn, L. J. (2013). *The selection, creation, and perception of interior spaces: An environmental psychology approach*.

Hammond, Z. (2015). *Culturally responsive teaching and the brain: Promoting authentic engagement and rigor among culturally and linguistically diverse students*. Corwin Press.

Kádek, K. I., & Tamáska, M. (2023). School buildings in the urban fabric as a result of 21st-century suburbanisation: Case studies on two middle-sized towns in the agglomeration of Budapest, Vác and Dunakeszi. *Land*, 12(8), 1576. <https://doi.org/10.3390/land12081576>

Kilgour, L., Matthews, N., Christian, P., & Shire, J. (2015). Health literacy in schools: Prioritising health and well-being issues through the curriculum. *Sport, Education and Society*, 20(4), 485–500.

Malaguzzi, L. (1994). Your image of the child: Where teaching begins. *Child Care Information Exchange*, 96, 52–56.

Maslow, A. H. (1943). A theory of human motivation. *Psychological Review*, 50(4), 370–396.
<https://doi.org/10.1037/h0054346>

Massaro, H. (2026a). *3D design before the holidays*. <https://planner5d.onelink.me/stDT/28s5clva>

Massaro, H. (2026b). *3D design after the holidays (SEL implementations)*.

<https://planner5d.onelink.me/stDT/ajhkeio9>

Massaro, H. (2026a). *Classroom after (post-intervention)*. 5D Planner.

<https://planner5d.onelink.me/stDT/guhjqmcl>

Massaro, H. (2026b). *Classroom before (pre-intervention)*. 5D Planner.

<https://planner5d.onelink.me/stDT/m8olkcdp>

Massaro, H. (2026c). *Intervention_Prototype_3D_Models_Video_Walkthrough*.

https://newuniversitymy.sharepoint.com/:f:/r/personal/hannah_massaro_student_nhlstenden_com/Documents/Intervention_Prototype_3D_Models_Video_Walkthrough?csf=1&web=1&e=hy3bSZ

McKenney, S., & Reeves, T. C. (2018). *Conducting educational design research* (2nd ed.). Routledge.

Osher, D., Cantor, P., Berg, J., Steyer, L., & Rose, T. (2020). Drivers of human development: How relationships and context shape learning and development. *Applied Developmental Science*, 24(1), 6–36. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10888691.2017.1398650>

Rinaldi, C. (2006). *In dialogue with Reggio Emilia: Listening, researching and learning*. Routledge.

Schonert-Reichl, K. A. (2023). Social and emotional learning: Its roots, what it is, how it works, what it does, and where it needs to go. *The Future of Children*, 33(1), 25–50.

<https://doi.org/10.1353/foc.2023.a902067>

School X. (2016, June 15). *Website of School X | International School in Madrid*.

Thornton, L., & Brunton, P. (2015). *Understanding the Reggio approach: Early years education in practice* (3rd ed.). Routledge.

VIBRA. (2026). *T1-D-4 – VIBRArch*. <https://www.vibrarch.upv.es/t1-d-4/>

Walford, G. (2021). Country houses repurposed as private schools: Building on inequality. *Oxford Review of Education*, 47(3), 369–385. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03054985.2020.1835629>

Wellington, J. (2015). *Educational research: Contemporary issues and practical approaches* (2nd ed.). Bloomsbury.

World Health Organization. (2022). *Child and adolescent mental and brain health*. <https://www.who.int/activities/improving-the-mental-and-brain-health-of-children-and-adolescents>

Appendices

Appendix 1A: Consent form shared with adults (teachers and specialists)

TEACHER QUESTIONNAIRE
Your Expertise Matters!

As part of my thesis research at Maxwell School, I'm collecting your professional insights on classroom design and its impact on children's SEL outcomes:

- Belonging
- Emotional safety
- Self-regulation
- Empathy & confidence
- Intrinsic motivation

Your anonymous responses will directly inform practical classroom improvements in the mixed Year 1–2 class!

Anonymous • Voluntary • Takes 10–15 minutes

Hannah Massaro
Fourth-year Student Teacher
International Teacher Education for Primary Schools
NHL Stenden University of Applied Sciences
hannah.massaro@student.nhlstenden.com
Thank you for your valuable expertise!
Maxwell School • Madrid

Teacher Consent Form for Classroom Research Project

Hannah Massaro
Calle Serrano 158
Madrid, 28002 Spain

24.03.2026

Dear Teacher,

I am Hannah Massaro, a fourth-year student teacher in my final year of the International Teacher Education for Primary Schools programme at NHL Stenden University of Applied Sciences in the Netherlands. During my placement at Maxwell School in Madrid, Spain, I will teach the mixed Year 1-2 classroom for 70-100% of the time, collaborating closely with the class teacher.

I am writing to seek your informed consent to participate in my research project titled “Optimising Classroom Design to Support Social-Emotional Learning (SEL) Outcomes in International Primary Settings.” The study focuses on creating a nurturing classroom environment that enhances students’ sense of belonging, emotional safety, self-regulation, empathy, confidence, and intrinsic motivation.

I would like to collect data based on your expertise and professional experience as a teacher. You can participate if you are currently teaching at Maxwell School.

What the research involves

The research will take place entirely during normal class time and will not disrupt the regular timetable. It includes fun, age-appropriate activities with the children (subject to separate parental/guardian consent and child assent) such as:

- drawings and creative tasks;
- completing simple, child-friendly questionnaires;
- short talks, discussions, or one-to-one/small-group interviews;
- group workshops; and
- the taking of pictures of classroom activities or children’s artwork (faces will be anonymised or blurred wherever possible).

As a participating teacher, you will be invited to contribute by completing a short questionnaire and/or participating in a brief interview about classroom design and observed SEL outcomes. Your input will draw directly on your expertise and experience. All activities are designed to be enjoyable and suitable for the age group.

Voluntary participation and your rights

- Participation (for both the children in the class and for yourself) is completely voluntary.
- You may withdraw consent at any time without giving a reason and without any negative consequences for you, the children, or the school.
- All data will be anonymised (names and identifying details removed) and stored securely in password-protected files in accordance with BERA Ethical Guidelines

(2018) and GDPR. Only I and my university supervisors will have access to the raw data.

- The research findings will be used to improve classroom design and SEL support at Maxwell School and may be shared in anonymised form in my final thesis and academic presentations.

Benefits

The information gathered will directly benefit the school by helping to create an even more supportive learning environment for all children and staff. There are no foreseeable risks.

Separate informed consent will be obtained from the parents/guardians of each child before any child participates.

If you have any questions about the research, please feel free to contact me at hannah.massaro@student.nhlstenden.com or speak directly with the school leadership.

How to respond

If you are happy for the research to be conducted in the classroom and for your own participation (based on your expertise and experience), please complete, sign and return this form to the school leadership by **2nd March 2026**. If you do not wish the research to proceed, no action is needed.

Consent Declaration

By signing this form, I confirm that I have read and understood the information provided above. I understand the purpose of the research, the activities involved (including questionnaires, potential interviews, and pictures), the voluntary nature of participation, my right to withdraw at any time, and how data will be protected. I confirm that I am currently teaching at Maxwell School. I hereby give my informed consent for the research project to be conducted and for my own participation based on my expertise and experience.

Teacher full name: _____

Signature: _____

Date: _____

Class / Role / Year group taught: _____

Thank you very much for your support and for helping to make this research possible. I look forward to working together to create a wonderful classroom experience!

Warm regards,

Hannah Massaro
Student Teacher
Maxwell School, Madrid

Appendix 1B: Consent form shared with parents of the students

Hannah Massaro
Calle Serrano 158
Madrid, 28002 Spain
February 18, 2026

Dear Parent/Guardian,

I am Hannah Massaro, a fourth-year student teacher in my final year of the International Teacher Education for Primary Schools program at NHL Stenden University of Applied Sciences in the Netherlands. During my placement at Maxwell School in Madrid, Spain, I will teach your child in the mixed Year 1-2 classroom for 70-100% of the time, collaborating with the class teacher.

I seek your informed consent for your child to participate in my research on optimizing classroom design to support social-emotional learning (SEL) outcomes like belonging, emotional safety, self-regulation, empathy, confidence, and intrinsic motivation. This study aims to create a nurturing environment that enhances students' well-being in international settings. Participation involves fun, age-appropriate activities like drawings, short talks, or group workshops integrated into class time.

This adheres to BERA Ethical Guidelines (2018), ensuring voluntary participation, withdrawal anytime without consequences, confidentiality via anonymization and secure storage, and child assent. Data benefits the school by improving SEL. Contact me at hannah.massaro@student.nhlstenden.com or the school with questions.

If you consent, sign and return the form below by 2nd March 2026. Otherwise, no action needed. Thank you!

Best regards,

Hannah Massaro

Email: hannah.massaro@student.nhlstenden.com

Consent Form

I consent to my child
participating voluntarily. We can withdraw anytime.

Signature: _____ Date: _____

Appendix 2A: Microsoft questionnaire completed by students

1. Student Code (filled in by researcher)

12
Responses

Latest Responses
 "Y1-05 – Noel"
 "Y1-04 – Genevieve"
 "Y1-02 – Rose"
 ...

7 respondents (58%) answered Y2 for this question.

– Sloane **Y2** Y1

2. Which zone on the emotional thermometer matches how you feel right now?

- Angry 1
- Frustrated 0
- Worried 1
- Sad 0
- Calm 6
- Happy 4

3. Do you feel you belong in this classroom? Why or why not?

12
Responses

Latest Responses
 "Yes because i can dance"
 "Mhm, because I am happy."
 "Yes, because it's cozy. I don't know what exactly."
 ...

4 respondents (33%) answered home for this question.

4. What makes you feel safe or unsafe in the room?

12 Responses

Latest Responses

- "Sometimes I'm scared because Manuel wants to fight"
- "Yes I feel safe in the classroom. Because I feel lovely."
- "Yes, but I don't know why."
- ...

3 respondents (25%) answered classroom for this question.

5. What do you do when you feel a strong emotion in class? (like angry, sad, or very happy)

12 Responses

Latest Responses

- "I go away to the bean bag"
- "I would play with the tablet in Spanish class with Miss Maria."
- "I don't know"
- ...

4 respondents (33%) answered happy for this question.

6. How easy it is for you to notice a friend is upset?

- Very easy 5
- A little easy 3
- Not so easy 4
- Not sure 0

7. Which area of the room helps you calm down the most? (you can point) What would make that area even better?

12
Responses

Latest Responses

- "I like you so I will hug you. Then I am calm again."
- "I like to sit in the puff chair the beanbag."
- "No, but I don't know how to create one either."
- ...

8. Do you prefer working...

- Alone at a desk 0
- In small groups 3
- Both - it depends on the day 9

9. How does the light in the room change how you feel during a lesson?

10. Do the pictures and displays on the walls feel like they are for you and your family? How does that make you feel?

11. What colours or symbols would best show how you feel over the day? (for our emotional thermometer)

5 respondents (42%) answered happy for this question.

A word cloud visualization of responses. The word "happy" is the largest and most prominent, centered in the cloud. Other words are smaller and arranged around it. The words include: "yellow", "calm", "rainbow", "sad and then blue", "blue", "color", "blue for calm", "blue every color", "Green blue", and "super super".

yellow calm rainbow
sad and then blue happy color
blue for calm blue every color Green blue
super super

Appendix 2B: Microsoft questionnaire completed by teachers and specialists

Responses Overview Active

Responses

8

Average Time

22:37

Duration

14

Days

1. Do you currently teach at Maxwell School?

- Yes 7
- No 1

2. Are you currently teaching (or co-teaching) in the mixed Year 1–2 classroom?

- Yes 4
- No 3
- Other 1

3. If you choose the option 'Other' in the question above please elaborate

1

Responses

Latest Responses

"I am the school secretary so see the classrooms although I do not teach there."

4. How many years of teaching experience do you have in total? Describe any important details

8

Responses

Latest Responses

"7 in academies"
 "10 years"
 "2"
 ...

5. How many years have you taught in early primary / Year 1–2 settings?

8
Responses

Latest Responses
"0"
"10 years"
"2"
...

6. Please briefly describe your current role in the Year 1–2 classroom (e.g., class teacher, co-teacher, specialist support).

8
Responses

Latest Responses
"Observer"
"Spanish teacher / head of primary"
"Co-teacher"
...

7. Classroom design (layout, seating, lighting, displays, zoning, and accessibility of materials) is an important factor in supporting children's social-emotional learning (SEL) outcomes.

Strongly agree	5
Agree	3
Disagree	0
Strongly disagree	0
Neutral	0

8. In your experience, intentional classroom design can be as influential as teaching strategies in creating a nurturing, home-like environment for young learners.

Neutral	0
Strongly disagree	0
Disagree	0
Agree	6
Strongly agree	2

9. To what extent do you believe the current classroom design supports the following SEL outcomes? (Rate most to least)

10. Please explain any SEL outcomes above that you rated as particularly well-supported (or not well-supported) by the current design. What specific design features (e.g., zoning, seating arrangements, displays, lighting) contribute to this?

7
Responses

Latest Responses

"I believe that from the times I have seen the students there in the current de..."
 "Displays, visual calendars, interactive resources, pictures of children as part o..."
 ...

11. Have you worked with children in your Year 1–2 classroom who displayed SEL-related challenges such as: (Select all that apply)

12. If you selected the option 'Other' in the question above please elaborate

0
Responses

0 responses submitted

...
 ...
 ...

13. In your experience, how does the current classroom design either help or hinder children showing the above SEL challenges? Please give one or two specific examples (e.g., a particular zone, seating arrangement, or accessibility issue).

5
Responses

Latest Responses

"I believe there is not enough space for self regulation and withdraw!"
 "For example, the calm area (currently with the pouf) is a very important spac..."
 ...

14. When planning or reflecting on classroom design, do you consider the accessibility of everyday materials (e.g., pencils, crayons, paper, books) for all children?

■ Yes, always	3
■ Yes, sometimes	5
■ No	0
■ Not applicable	0

15. Please explain how (or why not) accessibility of materials influences your classroom design decisions and children's learning experiences.

7
Responses

Latest Responses

"I believe it would improve their experience"
 "When materials are easily accessible, children are able to work more indepe..."
 ...

16. Rate how important the following design elements are for supporting SEL in a mixed Year 1–2 international classroom:

- Not important
- Somewhat important
- Neutral
- Important
- Extremely important

- Flexible zoning (e.g., calm corner, collaborative hubs)
- Seating arrangements (rows vs. clusters/pods)
- Lighting and colour palette (adjusted lightning, harmonic colors)
- Displays and visual materials (cultural responsiveness, student-created work)
- Accessibility and child-sized furniture (specific furniture for children)

17. To what extent do you agree that making everyday materials (like pencils) easily accessible?

■ Strongly agree	5
■ Agree	3
■ Neutral	0
■ Disagree	0
■ Strongly disagree	0

18.What is one feasible change you would propose to the current classroom design (layout, zoning, seating, lighting, displays, or accessibility) to better support SEL outcomes such as belonging, emotional safety, or self-regulation?

19.If we were to co-design a small prototype together (using existing school resources), what would be your top priority for improvement?

20.Are there any constraints at Maxwell School (budget, space, school policy, etc.) that we should consider when suggesting design adjustments?

21.Is there anything else you would like to share about how classroom design affects teaching and learning in the Year 1–2 classroom at Maxwell School?

22.By completing and submitting this questionnaire, I confirm that: • I have read and fully understood the attached "Teacher Consent Form – Hannah Massaro" (Word document). • I agree to all the terms and conditions mentioned in the consent form, including voluntary participation, right to withdraw at any time, anonymisation of data, secure storage, and use of my responses in the research, thesis, and possible academic presentations. • I confirm that I am currently teaching at Maxwell School. • I give my informed consent for my participation in this research project based on my expertise and experience.

Appendix 3: Interview with the Head of Primary pre intervention on March 17, 2026

1. What main benefits do you see if teachers take social emotional learning outcomes into consideration when setting up their classroom?
2. When we think about the classroom, what main benefits do you maybe see if teachers take that into consideration?
3. How could the fostering of feelings such as belonging, safety, self control and kindness help with student moving between countries, experiencing transitions and inclusion in the whole school atmosphere?
4. When thinking about redesigning the classroom to further nurture social emotional learning outcomes, do you think these changes can be made with the things we already have at school?
5. Could this team based way of changing the classroom support the school and maybe teacher goals for growth, global citizenship and also helping students who come and go?
6. If yes, how?
7. How could these ideas affect school rules or future classroom plans?
8. Would you support doing the same in other classes and what would we need for it to work?
9. Would you maybe say you can honestly share maybe your thoughts on that?
10. Would you use something like that if you were interested in how to incorporate social emotional learning outcomes, maybe online or maybe taking inspiration from that?
11. Would you also say or would you maybe agree with the fact that if we improve social emotional learning outcomes or social emotional behaviors that we can already see and observe daily in classrooms, like the ability to empathize with another person or that

student's self esteem or that student's intrinsic motivation to do something, so not being so dependent on the teacher, will automatically resume in better learning outcomes?

12. So therefore, should we take social emotional learning into consideration maybe when we design a classroom?

Appendix 4: Interview with the Head of School on March 23, 2026

1. What do you think about the classroom change?
2. How could we maybe use the 3D tool?
3. What kind of opportunities do you see there?
4. Would you say that a teacher that maybe wants to engage more or wants to implement more ESL learning strategies like the classroom as a third teacher could use this model that I designed to maybe also implement some changes themselves?
5. What ideas and opportunities do you maybe see there?
6. Would you say just from the 3D models alone that change and the support that the children get is even visible through just the 3D designs?

Appendix 5: Interview with the School Psychologist on March 25, 2026

1. From a whole school view and also your view as in a leadership role, what main benefits do you maybe see if teachers would take social emotional learning outcomes into consideration when setting up their classroom at the beginning of the year?
2. How could the fostering of feelings such as belonging, safety, self control and kindness help with students moving between countries, inclusion of all learners or the whole school atmosphere?

3. When thinking about redesigning the classroom to further nurture social emotional learning outcomes, do you think these changes can be made with the things we already have in school?
4. What main problems do you maybe see from your leadership side when a teacher maybe wants to change the classroom?
5. Do you think there could be problems or challenges?
6. But let's say someone wants to make some changes with the materials you already have in school?
7. So you would say involving students when there are changes being made is really important?
8. Could this team based way of changing the classroom, where colleagues are working collaboratively as it often happens in a school, foster teacher growth, global citizenship or helping students come and go?
9. So when teachers are working cooperatively, maybe students also get this sense of like, I'm being taken care of not just by one person but by multiple people?
10. How could ideas like this affect school rules or future classroom plans?
11. Would you support doing the same in other classes?
12. What would we need for it?
13. Would you say this intervention could be helpful for other teachers?

Appendix 6: Interview with the PSHE teacher pre intervention on March 23, 2026

1. In your experience as a PSHE teacher, how much consideration do classroom teachers generally give to social emotional learning outcomes such as belonging, emotional self regulation and empathy when they design or arrange the classroom spaces?

2. What constraints, for example the space, the budget, school policies, furniture availability or international nature of the student population at school, do you see that currently limit teachers from intentional design in classrooms to better support social emotional learning?
3. Looking at the current layout like seating, lighting and displays in this year one and two mixed classroom, which elements do you feel already promote emotional safety and connection and which ones might unintentionally create discomfort or reduce students agency?
4. Would you have maybe a recommendation or do you see some constraints?
5. So instead of having the tables right in the middle of the classroom, you would say for the zoning we could divide the tables and then maybe do something else there?
6. How do you think the frequent student transitions, for example incoming and outgoing families in this international school setting, affect the need for a more stable home like classroom environment?
7. Do you notice any SEL challenges linked to the current physical space during these transitions?
8. So how well do you think this current classroom fosters a home like feeling in the sense of like this is your home away maybe from the home that you came from?
9. In your PSHE lessons, have you observed moments where the classroom environment itself seemed to act as a third teacher, supporting or hindering children's emotional regulation or sense of belonging?
10. Can you give examples?

Appendix 7: Interview with the PSHE teacher post intervention on April 14, 2026

1. So you as a PSHE teacher, do you notice any behavioral changes of the students in connection to the classroom?
2. By changing this element of the classroom, which social emotional learning outcome, for example empathy or agency or something else, do you think is being fostered?
3. So would you also say this relates to maybe confidence?
4. Do you see another social emotional learning outcome being fostered through the changes that have been made in the classroom?
5. When you do your lessons, do you overall would say that disruptions or emotional needs are somewhat less compared to before the holidays with the original design of the classroom?

Appendix 8: Interview with the Head of Primary post intervention on April 30, 2026

1. What do you think about the classroom change?
2. I would now invite you to look at the 3D designs. You can take how much time you want.
This is after with healing. You're welcome to play around and let me know if you think teachers could utilize this tool. How could we maybe use it? What kind of opportunities you see there?
3. Would you say that a teacher that maybe wants to engage more or wants to implement more SEL learning strategies like the classroom as a third teacher, could use this model that I designed to maybe also implement some changes themselves or, yeah, what ideas and opportunities to maybe see there?
4. So would you say just from the 3D models alone, that change and the support that the children get is even visible through just the 3D designs?

Appendix 9: Intervention Design: Floor plan of the classroom before the changes; designed by Hannah Massaro

Appendix 10: Intervention Design: 3D model of the classroom before the changes; designed by Hannah Massaro

https://newuniversitymy.sharepoint.com/:f:/r/personal/hannah_massaro_student_nhlstenden_com/Documents/Intervention_Prototype_3D_Models_Video_Walkthrough?csf=1&web=1&e=hy3bS

[Z](#)

Appendix 11: Intervention Design: Floor plan of the classroom after the changes; designed by Hannah Massaro

Appendix 12: Intervention Design: 3D model of the classroom after the changes; designed by Hannah Massaro

https://newuniversitymy.sharepoint.com/:f:/r/personal/hannah_massaro_student_nhlstenden_com/Documents/Intervention_Prototype_3D_Models_Video_Walkthrough?csf=1&web=1&e=hy3bS

[Z](#)

